

VEXAS SYNDROME: A MONOGENIC DISEASE

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Abstract

VEXAS (Vacuoles, E1 enzyme, X-linked, Auto inflammatory, Somatic) syndrome is a monogenic disease that cause inflammatory and hematologic manifestations. UBA1 (Ubiquitin like Modifier Activating Enzyme) variants acquired during a person's lifetime cause VEXAS syndrome and result in the production of an enzyme with reduced function. As a result, damaged or unneeded proteins build up inside cells instead of being broken down, which may contribute to abnormal activation of immune cells or cell damage and death. When UBA1 gene variants occur in immune cells or blood cells, they lead to abnormal inflammation, impaired blood cell development, and other features of VEXAS syndrome. This article discuss about the various systems that will be affected, its manifestations and therapeutic options for VEXAS syndrome.

Keywords – VEXAS, UBA1, Immunity, Inflammation, Gene variant

I. INTRODUCTION

VEXAS syndrome is a late onset monogenic disease that causes inflammatory and hematologic manifestations. This is caused by the somatic mutation in the UBA1 (Ubiquitin Like Modifier Activating Enzyme) gene of blood cells.¹ Somatic mutations that affect the methionine at amino acid position forty one in UBA1, coding for one of the two known E1 ubiquitylation enzymes, were shown to cause this disorder, which the authors named the VEXAS syndrome^{2,3}. VEXAS is an acronym for Vacuoles, E1 enzyme, X-linked, Auto inflammatory, Somatic. VEXAS affects various systems it was difficult to diagnose the disease and manage it. This article explains various systems affected, its manifestations and suggestions for its pharmacological management.

A. Ubiquitin Like Modifier Activating Enzyme

UBA1 (Ubiquitin Like Modifier Activating Enzyme) is a protein coding gene. The protein encoded by this gene provides instructions for making the ubiquitin-activating enzyme E1. This enzyme is necessary for the ubiquitin-proteasome system, which targets damaged or unneeded proteins to be broken down (degraded) within cells. Protein degradation helps maintain the proper balance of protein production and breakdown (protein homeostasis). Old proteins need to be removed to make way for new proteins to allow cells to function and survive. The ubiquitin-proteasome system acts as the cell's quality control system by disposing of damaged, misshapen, and excess proteins.

Ubiquitin-activating enzyme E1 is responsible for the first step in the ubiquitin-proteasome system; it turns on (activates) a small protein called ubiquitin. With the assistance of other proteins, the active ubiquitin attaches to a protein that is to be broken down. When a chain of ubiquitin proteins is attached to a protein, the protein is recognized and destroyed by a complex of enzymes called a proteasome^{5,6}.

B. UBA1 gene variant and VEXAS

UBA1 gene variants acquired during a person's lifetime and are present only in certain immune cells and blood-forming cells in the bone marrow. This variants cause VEXAS syndrome and result in the production of an enzyme with reduced function. As a result, damaged or unneeded proteins build up inside cells instead of being broken down, which may contribute to abnormal activation of immune cells or cell damage and death. This protein buildup also disrupts protein homeostasis. Old proteins must be removed before cells can make new proteins. If damaged or unneeded proteins are not broken down, they can stop the production of new proteins, which can contribute to the impairment of normal cell functions. When the immune system detects accumulation of damaged or unneeded proteins (it will be considered as antigen), it triggers an immune response to protect the body. Inflammation is a part of this immune response. Immune cells, such as macrophages and dendritic cells recognize the presence of the harmful stimuli or antigens. They act as sentinels, patrolling the body to identify any potential threats. Once the immune cells detect these harmful substances, they release signaling molecules called cytokines. These cytokines communicate with other immune cells, amplifying the immune response. The release of cytokines leads to the dilation of blood vessels in the affected area, increasing blood flow to the site of infection or injury. This results in redness and warmth in the area. The blood vessel walls become more permeable, allowing immune cells and fluid to move from the blood vessels into the affected tissue. This causes swelling and pain. Immune cells, such as neutrophils and white blood cells, are recruited to the site of inflammation to attack and eliminate the pathogens or foreign substances. When *UBA1* gene variants occur in immune cells or blood cells, they lead to abnormal inflammation, impaired blood cell development, and other features of VEXAS syndrome^{7,8}.

II. SYSTEM AFFECTED AND ITS PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

A. Bone marrow

As VEXAS is an auto inflammatory condition, it involves chronic inflammation due to deregulated immune responses. This prolonged inflammation can create an environment in the bone marrow that is not conducive to normal blood cell production. This prolonged inflammation can disrupt the microenvironment that supports stem cell differentiation and maturation, leading to the production of abnormal and ineffective blood cells, which is a characteristic of MDS (myelodysplastic syndromes). Chronic inflammation in the bone marrow, which is responsible for production of blood cells, leads to anemia, leucopenia, and thrombocytopenia.

As there is a compromisation of protein degradation pathway, unneeded proteins can accumulate and be less effectively cleared from the cell. Overload of these proteins leads to stress of endoplasmic reticulum. This triggers a cellular stress response that aims to restore protein homeostasis. If the cellular stress response is unable to alleviate the stress, it can lead to cell dysfunction and vacuolization^{9,10,11}.

B. Pulmonary system

When the respiratory system encounters the foreign particle or antigen, the immune system responds to protect the lungs. Here, the protein aggregates are considered as antigen. Immune cells, such as macrophages and dendritic cells in the lungs recognize and engulf the invading particles. They release cytokines to signal other immune cells, initiating the inflammatory response. Cytokines lead to the dilation of blood vessels in the lungs, increasing blood flow to the affected area. This allows immune cells, particularly neutrophils and white blood cells, to migrate from the blood vessels into the lung tissues to combat the allergen. The blood vessel walls in the lungs become more permeable, allowing fluid and immune cells to leak into the lung tissue, leading to swelling and pulmonary infiltration. During the immune response, the immune cells release enzymes and reactive oxygen species to kill pathogens. However, these substances can also damage healthy lung tissue, contributing to the pulmonary infiltration. As the immune system eliminates the irritant, the inflammation gradually subsides, and the lung tissue starts to heal. In some cases, chronic inflammation may persist, leading to ongoing pulmonary infiltration and potential lung damage. Thus the most commonly described pulmonary manifestation was pulmonary infiltrates, often found to co-exist with other lung pathologies such as NSIP (nonspecific interstitial pneumonia), pulmonary vasculitis and pleural effusion^{12, 13}.

C. Blood and blood vessels

In the blood vessels, as part of the immune response, there is an inflammation. This inflammation can damage the inner lining of the blood vessels, known as endothelium. Activated endothelial cells can also release molecules that attract platelets and promote their adhesion, which is an early step in clot formation. Exposing the underlying tissues and promoting the adhesion of immune cells and platelets further exacerbate inflammation and clot formation. Thus there is vasculitis in this syndrome. Inflammatory responses can also trigger the release of procoagulant factors and cytokines, which can shift the balance of the clotting system towards a more prothrombotic state. This increased coagulation activity can lead to clot formation more readily. The dynamics of blood flow in veins and arteries are different. Arteries carry oxygen rich blood away from the heart and have a high pressure and faster blood flow than veins. The slower blood flow in veins can lead to the pooling of blood and a higher likelihood of clot formation in veins than in arteries^{14, 15}.

D. Cartilage

Auto inflammatory conditions could potentially impact cartilage as well. Deregulation of cytokines, which are small signaling molecules that play a crucial role in immune responses and inflammation leads to an overactive immune response and inflammation within the cartilage. It leads to polycondritis or relapsing polycondritis. Relapsing polycondritis can also involve inflammation of blood vessels, which may contribute to tissue damage and the clinical manifestations of the disease. Relapsing polycondritis can affect various parts of the body, including the ears, nose, joints, respiratory tract, and other cartilage rich areas. This can lead to a wide range of symptoms, including pain, swelling, deformities and dysfunction of affected structures¹⁶.

III. MANIFESTATIONS

Lung pathologies was found to be one of the most common clinical features of VEXAS and associated with mortality. Pulmonary embolism was identified in VEXAS co-existing with haemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis and also with Kikuchi-Fujimoto disease (an autoinflammatory condition characterized by necrotizing lymphadenitis and fever).

Incidence of venous thromboembolic events in VEXAS has been reported as being as high as 36% while arterial thrombotic events have an estimated incidence of 1.6%. A study by Beck *et al.*, included 25 patients with somatic mutation and in such patients, an often fatal, treatment-refractory inflammatory syndrome develops in late adulthood, with fevers, cytopenias, characteristic vacuoles in myeloid and erythroid precursor cells, dysplastic bone marrow, neutrophilic cutaneous and pulmonary inflammation, chondritis, and vasculitis. Most of the patients included in the study met clinical criteria for an inflammatory syndrome (relapsing polycondritis, Sweet's syndrome, polyarteritis nodosa, or giant-cell arteritis) or a hematologic condition (myelodysplastic syndrome or

multiple myeloma) or both¹⁷. Ferrada *et al.*, conducted a study with 92 patients. In that the patients commonly had fever, ear chondritis, skin involvement, deep vein thrombosis, and pulmonary infiltrates. Macrocytic anemia, thrombocytopenia, lymphopenia, multiple myeloma, myelodysplastic syndrome were also prevalent in VEXAS¹⁶. A case series study by Vander *et al.*, included 12 patients with mutation in UBA1 gene. These patients had systemic symptoms – fever, weight loss, night sweats. In skin they had Erythematous plaque and red purple papules, Erythema nodosum. They also had macrocytic anemia, thrombocytopenia, pancytopenia, chondritis of the ear, arthritis, blepharitis, etc¹⁸. In a study by Temple and Kosmider, patients with VEXAS was often presented with intermittent and unexplained fevers, fatigue, myalgia, with a constellation of inflammatory symptoms affecting the skin, cartilage, joints, lungs and blood vessels¹⁹. Lavielle *et al.*, conducted a study with 116 patients with VEXAS syndrome who were referred to a multicentre registry. In that study the main clinical features of VEXAS syndrome were found to be skin lesions (83%), non infectious fever (64%), weight loss (62%), lung involvement (50%), ocular symptoms (39%), relapsing chondritis (36%), venous thrombosis (35%), lymph nodes (34%), arthralgia (27%). They also found that the hematological disease (myelodysplastic syndrome (n=58), monoclonal gammopathy of unknown significance (n=12)) was present in 58 cases (50%).¹²

Obiorah *et al* reported an higher rate of venous thromboembolism at 56.25% (nine out of 16 patients), with 60% of thrombotic events occurring within the first two years of disease onset¹⁴. In a study by Thet Mon Oo *et al.*, seven patients were observed to have recurrent venous thromboembolism with a median of two events per patient, with three patients were noted to have recurrent venous thromboembolisms despite being on therapeutic anticoagulation. Apart from venous thromboembolism, there were also arterial thrombotic events reported including transient ischaemic attack, ischaemic stroke, and myocardial infarction. A rapid literature review showed that the incidence of venous thromboembolism (36.4%) is markedly higher than arterial thrombosis (1.6%). Of the 35 reported VTE (venous thromboembolism) cases specifying the location of thrombosis, 33 cases had DVT (deep vein thrombosis), while only eight cases had PE (pulmonary embolism). There were six cases of concurrent DVT and PE²⁰. In a case series by Koster *et al.*, refractory constitutional symptoms (88%), ear and nose chondritis (55%), and inflammatory arthritis (55%) were common clinical features. Vasculitis was noted in 44% and all patients had significantly elevated inflammatory markers and macrocytic anemia. Thrombocytopenia (66%) was present at the time of diagnosis of VEXAS. In that bone marrow biopsies was performed in eight patients and in that all bone marrows were hypercellular, and there was vacuolization of the erythroid (100%) or myeloid precursors (75%)²¹. A wide range of skin presentations are reported in VEXAS, including Sweet-like urticated and tender erythematous nodules, cartilaginous involvement with chondritis, cutaneous vasculitis, and periorbital angiodema. Sweet syndrome, relapsing polychondritis, polyarteritis nodosa, or erythema nodosum had been diagnosed in many patients. Hallmarks of skin histopathology are a neutrophilic dermatosis with coexisting or exclusive leukocytoclastic vasculitis.

VEXAS can be suspected in a patient who has an overlap of inflammatory and hematologic manifestations. In patients with VEXAS there is an elevation in the inflammatory markers such as C-Reactive protein and Erythrocyte sedimentation rate^{22, 23}.

IV. MANAGEMENT

There is no standardized treatment for VEXAS currently; however the inflammatory features can be treated with steroids and other immunosuppressants. The therapeutic options for VEXAS syndrome are an unmet need because, this is a severe and often progressive condition in most patients with multiorgan involvement and about half of the patients have an associated hematological malignancy such as myelodysplastic syndrome or monoclonal gammopathy and/or multiple myeloma and also most of the patients experience glucocorticoid dependency and associated complications²⁴.

As VEXAS is due to mutated UBA1 cells, eradicating the UBA1 mutated cells theoretically offers the possibility of cure. For that, allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation seems the most likely way. A study by Diarra *et al.*, retrospectively identified six patients with VEXAS syndrome who underwent allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation. In that study, ASCT (autologous stem cell transplant) was guided by life-threatening autoinflammatory symptoms that were refractory to multiple therapies and after 32, 37, 38 months three patients are in durable complete remission. Two are in complete remission response after three and five months and in post transplantation one died unfortunately. The report of that study suggests that ASCT could be a curative option in patients with VEXAS syndrome and severe manifestations. Considering the complications and side effects of the

procedure as well as the existence of other therapeutic options, clinical trials are required to define the subgroup of patients who will benefit from this strategy and its place in the therapeutic arsenal against VEXAS syndrome^{25, 26, 27}.

Drugs targeting cytokines (Interluken 1, Interluken 3, Tumor necrosis factor alpha) and the effector cells signaling pathways like JAK (janus kinase) inhibitors, calcineurin inhibitors, corticosteroids, and other immunosuppressive medications have been used empirically in VEXAS patients prior to the identification of their underlying UBA1 mutation²⁵.

Among the strategies targeting the immune system, responses were observed with corticosteroids, but relapses or corticosteroid dependence limited their effectiveness over time. More interesting results were found with tocilizumab, cyclosporine, and JAK inhibitors.

In the study by Heiblig *et al*, the authors describe evidence of significant treatment efficacy with the preferential JAK inhibitor ruxolitinib. Other JAK inhibitors also seem to have some, albeit lesser efficacy in treating VEXAS syndrome. The authors describe 30 patients treated with JAK inhibitors. At months one, three, and six after beginning treatment with a JAK inhibitor, a clinical response was seen in 50%, 57%, and 82%, respectively, of those remaining on treatment. These overall results masked the marked discrepancies between individual JAK inhibitors; rates of clinical remission favored ruxolitinib over other JAK inhibitors at 67% vs 38% at one month, 83% vs 18% at three months, and 87% vs 11% at month six. There was also a marked steroid dose reduction of 83.6% with ruxolitinib and 75% with other JAK inhibitors; three patients stopped glucocorticoid treatment entirely. The significant reductions in glucocorticoid dose suggest that the benefit of JAK inhibitors other than ruxolitinib is possibly greater than would be suggested by the headline numbers, because patients with VEXAS syndrome tend to be extremely resistant to glucocorticoid reduction. The majority of patients who stopped JAK inhibitors did so because of lack of efficacy, and the majority of those were receiving drugs other than ruxolitinib. Infections and thromboembolic disease were common, but these are already common complications of VEXAS syndrome, so the results are difficult to interpret^{28, 29}.

A study by Bindoli *et al.*, concluded that even though glucocorticoids often represent the first line therapy and blood transfusion support is usually required, the promising results derived from JAK-inhibitors, in particular selective JAK-1 (filgotinib, upadacitinib), or JAK1/2 blockers (ruxolitinib), may represent a suitable therapeutic approach. Larger cohorts are necessary to establish, JAK inhibitors are candidable as first-line therapy in VEXAS. The wide heterogeneity of the clinical presentations of the syndrome requires an accurate and more extensive clusterization of patients that will be essential for the correct clinical and therapeutic management³⁰.

Hypomethylating agent azacytidine is also shown to be effective in VEXAS syndrome associated with DNMT3A (DNA methyltransferase 3 alpha) mutations. Even though there is a consideration of treatment with azacytidine on a trial basis in severe cases of VEXAS syndrome when associated with DNMT3A mutations, future clinical trials will be pivotal to investigate the exact value of azacytidine in subsets of patients with VEXAS syndrome^{31, 32}.

Prednisone treatment in a dose regimen 20-50 mg daily offers good symptomatic relief, but such treatment, especially in longer duration is usually associated with severe adverse effects typical for glucocorticoids. Therefore, it should be applied during shortest possible period of time in the lowest possible dose to achieve a clinical effect. Careful benefit-risk assessment must be implemented for every patient suffering from VEXAS, and especially in cases in which all therapeutic options have been exhausted and the last line for symptom-control is a chronic therapy with corticosteroids. There are individual cases of patients who responded well on ruxolitinib, tocilizumab, rituximab and cyclosporine allowing the reduction of the steroid-based therapy, but there are also reports on tocilizumab-related serious adverse effects, including interstitial nephritis, stroke, cardiac involvement and intestinal perforation³³.

V. CONCLUSION

All currently available anti-TNF, anti-IL-1, anti-IL-6, and anti-IL-8 medications should be taken into consideration as potential study subjects, along with genetic anti-UBA-1 therapy, based on preclinical results. However, due to the complexity of the illness and the wide inter-individual variation in clinical response to various therapy alternatives among VEXAS patients, it is highly likely that individualized therapeutic approaches will be required for this disease.

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